

MEANS OF EXPRESSING DEFINITENESS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to discuss different means of obtaining definiteness in English. It is well known that English, along with other European languages, have a closed set of elements which must be employed lexically in order to render definite or indefinite expression and this system consists mainly of articles. As a matter of fact, I chose to analyze the methods by means of which noun phrases in English obtain definite interpretation, and this classification does not resort only to articles, but to other categories as well. One important aspect is the problem of referentiality with two conditions that must be accomplished, namely the uniqueness condition and that of individuality

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1.0. Means of Expressing Definiteness in English

'*Definite*' and '*indefinite*' are terms that are usually applied to noun phrases (NPs). In English, *the* is referred to as '*the definite article*,' and *a/an* as '*the indefinite article*.' Noun phrases (NPs) that begin with *the* (e.g., *the Queen of England*, *the book*), which are also called (especially in the philosophical literature) '*definite descriptions*,' are generally taken to be prototypical examples of definite NPs in English. However, it should be noted that not all of them show the same pieces of behavior that have come to be taken as criteria for definiteness. Similarly, NPs that begin with '*a/an*' (*an elephant*, *a big lie*), '*indefinite descriptions*,' are prototypical examples of indefinite NPs. (Plural indefinite descriptions use the determiner '*some*'.)

Exactly what differentiates definite from indefinite NPs has been a matter of some dispute. One tradition comes from the philosophical literature, more specifically Bertrand Russell's classic work on denoting phrases (Russell, 1905). On this tradition, what distinguishes *the* from *a/an* is uniqueness – more specifically the existence of one and only one item matching the descriptive content of the NP. So, while the use of an indefinite description in a simple, positive sentence merely asserts the existence of an item matching the description, the usage of a definite item asserts its uniqueness as an addition to that regard. While (1a), on this view, is paraphrasable as (1b), (1c) is equivalent to (1d).

- (1) (a) I met a potential buyer for this stray cat.
(b) There is at least one buyer of the stray cat whom I met.
(c) I met the buyer of the stray cat.
(d) There is one and only one buyer of the stray cat, and I met him.

On his account both indefinite and definite expressions are quantificational in nature (like explicitly quantified NPs, such as *every strawberry*, *no unwanted intruders*). The quantificational interpretation of definite items has been questioned by others, who view these NPs instead as referential

(Strawson, 1950; Hawking, 1978). The uniqueness theory seems to accord well with our intuitions. It also is supported by the fact that when we stress the definite article contrastively, it brings out the sense of uniqueness.

It might seem that this approach would necessarily be confined to singular NPs. However, as argued by Hawkins (1978), the idea of exhaustiveness is able to extend the notion of uniqueness to plurals alike, meaning that definite denotations consist of every descriptive note of the semantic content in a NP. A Noun Phrase like *the buyers of the stray cat* would be considered striking similar to *all the buyers of the stray cat*. The first challenge to Russell's ideas of definite descriptions was introduced by P. F. Strawson, who argued that definite descriptions in sentences with an entity meeting the descriptive content are not used to assert the existence and uniqueness of that entity. Instead, Strawson argued, definite descriptions are referential NPs, and the existence and uniqueness of a referent is supposed by itself (Strawson, 1950).

Another, more poignant difficulty for Russell's analysis has attracted more attention recently, namely the descriptive content of a definite syntagm does not suffice the criterion of unique reference in a great number of cases, perhaps the vast majority. One example of such an '*incomplete description*' is in (3):

3. Please put this on the chair.

The sentence in (3) is easily comprehensible despite the known fact that the universe comprises millions of chairs. This problem can be dealt with by means of two methods. A syntactic solution would make the NP contain the sufficient descriptive material tacitly— e.g., *the chair near to the table in the courtyard of the house at Oregon, Eastwood, California, USA*. However, the addressee would find it difficult to guess which descriptive content is understandable by itself. The uniqueness encoded in definite descriptions are bound to a relative context which makes it approachable, which include the items present in the universe of discourse participants and those items known by them in the course of the conversation or understood to be relevant to its topic. However, authors

like James McCawley (1979) found certain limitations to this theory, since two morphologically identical elements do not present sufficient properties in order to describe the uniqueness criterion"

4. The dog got into a fight with another dog.

David Lewis proposed that definite notions describe the most salient entity meeting its descriptive content (Lewis, 1979). Christophersen (1939) has introduced familiarity as playing a key role in the analyses of determiners in terms of definiteness. More recently, the influential work of Heim (1982) considers that anaphoricity resides as the basic meaning of definiteness. Like Strawson, Heim argued that definite descriptions are not so much quantificational, but referential. However, her theory is limited in that she also argued that indefinite descriptions are referential as well. Heim took the employment of definite and indefinite expressions as they occur in (5) as a direct result of their semantics. She argues that indefinite descriptions are subject to a `Novelty` condition: the condition is that the semantic content is introduced for the first time.

5. John saw *a movie* last week. *The movie* was not very intriguing.

In the discourse of (5), the indefinite NP `a movie` is employed to introduce a new note in the discourse. The anaphor is referred to with a definite (*the movie*). External factors usually do not restrict the domain of reference in uniqueness-based cases. Heim posits that definites act as anaphors in that a familiar discourse entity is referred back to. Familiarity is obtained when a semantic note has been either explicitly introduced into the universe (*strong familiarity*) or the context implicitly contains it (*weak familiarity*). Heim (1982) employs the metaphor of file cards, following Kamp's (1981) idea of a Discourse Representation. When describing anaphora, the notion of familiarity comes in handy, but the uniqueness effects intrinsically exist. Roberts (2003:290) notices that sentences like (6) pose a threat for the familiarity hypothesis because they refer to discourse-new entities and semantic uniqueness introduces the notion by itself.

6. He opened the elevator and pushed down the chair he found inside.

Here, the referent of the DP `the chair he found inside` is novel in the universe in such a way that weak familiarity does not even apply. Uniqueness is at stake here as implication in the Russellian sense (contextual restrictions). The felicitous utterance applies only when there is a single chair inside the elevator. Roberts goes further and unites uniqueness with Heim's approach by linking definite expressions with the existence of weak familiarity which contains a unique referent.

Though definite descriptions seem to fall very well under familiarity for a number of cases, it does not necessarily cover all the cases. One of these consists of definite descriptions where the unique referent is included by the descriptive content of the Noun Phrase and is independent from the context. Some examples are given in (7).

7. (a) John asked the smartest student in the room to explain everything.

(b) Larry opposed the idea that possibilities are extremely finite.

The referents of the underlined NPs are not necessarily acknowledged here by the addressees and they might also not have been mentioned previously in the conversation. We also observe that in such a case, the use of indefinite articles is prohibited:

8. (a) * John asked an smartest student in the room to explain everything.

(b) * Larry opposed an idea that possibilities are extremely finite.

When a unique referent relative to the whole world cannot be determined sufficiently by the descriptive content, there are cases this unique referent is found in a certain context and determined by the content. For these occurrences, one may employ the definite article, even if the addressee doesn't possess informations about the subject or the universe talked about. An example is given in (9):

9. Mary is sad because the broker who paid for the bet mistook his fee.

Following Lewis (1979), the notion of accommodation is invoked by supporters of familiarity, to account for these peculiarities. Addressees are usually trying to figure out which is the intended referent in order to accept a definite description. Since definite descriptions fall under the circumstances of both the uniqueness theory and the familiarity theory, there are also exceptions that don't match these criteria. One such column of examples is given in (10), of which Du Bois (1980) points out that employing an indefinite article forces the location to be semantically underlined, in a not so welcomed manner that puts the focus on inappropriate details:

10. (a) His father scribbled letters on *the wall*.

(b) We camped in front of *a river*.

(c) She hit herself in *the foot* with *a hammer*.

1.3. Conclusions of This Section

The main methods to express definiteness in English are through the employment of definite and indefinite articles and through the usage of demonstratives along with possessives. Unlike Japanese, English has the advantage that both Number is expressed through the employment of plural marker -s while Gender is not overtly expressed just like in Japanese. Definiteness can be dealt with in terms of uniqueness and familiarity as logic forms that derive from contextual reference. We bring into discussion the importance of context for English, even though it is not a necessary topic due to the presence of articles, because in Japanese the definite interpretation of a NP resides mostly on anaphoricity and cataphoricity of the contextual reference within different clauses. This does not mean that Japanese resorts only to ambiguous processes like contextual reference, as we will see in the next chapters.

The difference between definite and indefinite interpretations for English NPs brings into discussion one of the major characteristics of English nouns, namely that they are inherently non-definite, unlike Japanese, which has been shown, through null-NPs to

possess inherently definite nouns, even though the demonstration is still highly debatable in the literature. The previous observation is supported by the fact that the indefinite character of a noun in English is overtly marked, that is, through the employment of an indefinite article, which means that nouns must represent a different nature in terms of definiteness, other than that of the dichotomy definite/indefinite and that is the tertiary non-definite nature.

One argument comes from the idea that nouns in English cannot be grammatical in their lexicon status, more specifically, they cannot occur in sentences in their non-definite nature. What distinguishes *the* from *a/an* is uniqueness –the existence of an entity meeting the descriptive content of the NP. While the use of an indefinite description in a simple, sentence merely asserts the existence of an entity, the use of a definite description asserts in addition its uniqueness in that regard. Familiarity, on the other hand, comes hand in hand with the uniqueness criterion in that it presents the entity described as part of the universe of the

observerer, unlike uniqueness which presents the object as part of the general universe.

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